

Rearing yellow stem borer (YSB) for screening varietal resistance

R. C. Saxena, F. G. Medrano, and L. M. Sumio, Entomology Department, IRRI

YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker) moths lay eggs on rice plant leaves. Shortly after hatching, the neonate larvae bore into the plant tissues. Larval feeding at the vegetative and reproductive stages causes deadhearts (DH) and whiteheads.

Many cultivars are susceptible to YSB, and even moderate host plant resistance is

highly desirable. We developed a procedure to rear stem borers year-round, to help speed screening for varietal resistance.

Seedlings of IR62 (susceptible to YSB, resistant to other insect and tungro viruses) are transplanted weekly in 34- × 25- × 11-cm plastic trays (see figure). At mid-booting, a 2.5-cm-long slit is made with a scalpel in the bulging middle portion of the leaf sheath below the flag leaf. The incision is dilated to expose a small portion of the developing panicle. One to two first-instar YSB larvae are released onto the panicle and the incision closed.

At 25-30 d after infestation (DI), when larvae have pupated, plants are cut 15 cm above the base. The trays with stubbles are transferred to a 2- × 1- × 1-m screen cage for adult emergence. About 80% of the infested tillers produce moths.

Emerging moths are collected daily and transferred to oviposition cages with potted 40-d-old TN1 plants. Leaf cuts with egg masses are removed from those plants two times a week and placed in 15- × 1.5-cm test tubes or small ball jars.

At 27 ± 2 °C, eggs hatch in about a week. Emerging larvae are used for varietal screening, for basic studies, or for maintaining the insect culture. ■

Steps in rearing YSB for resistance studies.

MDU3, a new gall midge-resistant rice

S. Jebaraj, G. Soundarapandian, M. Subramanian, M. S. Venugopal, and G. Logeswaran, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Madurai 625104, Tamil Nadu, India

Our breeding work for gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzae* Wood Mason resistance identified a superior rice culture ACM8. In screenhouse and field tests in the endemic area, ACM8 yielded higher than highly susceptible IR20. ACM8 has been released as MDU3 exclusively for the GM endemic area.

MDU3 (IET6012) is a derivative of a cross involving IR8 and Warangal 1263. Grain yields in experiment station trials averaged 4.7 t/ha, 22.4% higher than IR20 (Table 1). In adaptive farmers' field trials at 24 locations, ACM8 yields averaged 4.9 t/ha, 10.9% higher than IR20. In na-

Table 1. Overall performance of MDUJ and IR20 in Tamil Nadu, India.

Trial	MDU3	IR20	Increase over IR20 (%)
<i>Grain yield (t/ha)</i>			
Research station trials ^a	4.7	3.8	22.4
Adaptive research trials ^b	4.9	4.4	10.9
AICRIP trial ^c	4.1	3.8	7.9
<i>Productivity/d (kg/ha)</i>			
	41.4	30.9	13.7

^aMean of 6 yr. ^bMean of 24 locations. ^cMean of 7 centers.